

Synthesis, characterization and antifungal activity of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadiensemicarbazone and amino acids

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Manuscript received 20 February 2007, accepted 6 March 2007

Abstract : A novel ligand viz. *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadiensemicarbazone (CDO SC) has been synthesized and characterized. Complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with CDO SC and amino acids, viz. L-alanine (L-ala), L-valine (L-val) and L-phenylalanine (L-phe), are reported. These ligands lead to the complexes of type [M(CDO SC)(AA)(H₂O)Cl], where AA = L-ala, L-val and L-phe. All the complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molecular weight, IR and UV-visible spectroscopy and magnetic susceptibility data. The investigated complexes are mononuclear. In these complexes, CDO SC and amino acids show bidentate coordination. The coordination of CDO SC is through azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen, while in amino acid the coordination is through carboxylate and neutral amino groups. The complexes are paramagnetic and possess an octahedral geometry.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, semicarbazone, amino acids.

In continuation of our previous work¹ present paper deals with the synthesis and characterization of new metallic complexes obtained from *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadiensemicarbazone (CDO SC) a derivative of *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienal (citral) and amino acids, viz. L-alanine, L-valine and L-phenylalanine. Metal ion mediated reaction involving ligands having N, O donor² atoms and amino acid side chains have been the subject of several investigations. We present here the synthesis and structural characterization of new metallic complexes between cobalt, nickel and copper dichlorides, CDO SC and amino acids (L-ala, L-val and L-phe). The coordinating properties of some semicarbazone metallic complexes have been studied³.

To obtain a better understanding of these *in vivo* mixed ligand complexes, model *in vitro* ternary complexes are being extensively investigated. Ligand CDO SC acts as a bidentate ligand with two potential metal ion binding sites, viz. oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. Amino acids also act as a bidentate ligands coordinating through the carboxylate oxygen and the amino nitrogen. Distorted octahedral geometry for Cu^{II} and octahedral geometries for both Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are predicted. The copper complexes of semicarbazone, oxime, phenylhydrazone and thiosemicarbazone derivatives are found to be potent cytotoxic agents in both murine and human tissue cultured cell lines as well as in solid tumors⁴.

Results and discussion

Analytical data of complexes are shown in Table 1 which are consistent with their molecular formula. All the complexes are non-hygroscopic in nature, stable at room temperature and decompose on heating at ~300 °C. These complexes are insoluble in water, slightly soluble in common organic solvents but readily soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductivity data of these complexes lie between 0.88–2.24 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMF (10⁻³ M) solution at room temperature and are consistent with their non electrolytic nature.

The IR spectra of newly synthesized mixed ligand complexes are given in Table 2. The spectra show characteristic band positions, shifts and intensities in comparison with free semicarbazone and respective free amino acids which can be correlated to bidentate semicarbazone binding and bidentate amino acid chelation. Besides this, binding of water⁵ molecules is also evident from IR spectra. The spectrum of CDO SC shows two strong bands at 3475 cm⁻¹ and 3284 cm⁻¹ attributed respectively to ν(N–H) asymmetric and ν(N–H) symmetric vibrations of terminal NH₂ group⁶. Two medium intensity bands at 3160 cm⁻¹ and 3080 cm⁻¹ are attributed to N–H stretching vibration of imino group. The band appearing at 1625 cm⁻¹ is due to ν(C=N) while other at 948 cm⁻¹ is due to ν(N–N). The stretching vibration of carbonyl group is observed at 1690 cm⁻¹.

Table 1. Analytical data of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *cis*-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienemicarbazone and amino acids (*L*-ala or *L*-val or *L*-pht)

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Yield (g, %)	m.p. (d) (°C)	Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	Found (Calcd.) %				μ_{eff} (B.M.) ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	A_m
						C	H	N	Cl		
1.	[Co(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -ala)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Pink	0.56,	260	400.5 (409.8)	41.1 (41.0)	6.8 (6.6)	13.6 (13.4)	8.4 (8.6)	4.0	1.32
	[CoC ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					43.8 (43.9)	7.1 (7.1)	12.6 (12.7)	8.2 (8.1)		
2.	[Co(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -val)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Pink	0.59,	270	426.2 (437.8)	43.9 (43.9)	6.3 (6.4)	11.6 (11.5)	7.6 (7.3)	4.2	1.93
	[CoC ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					41.1 (41.1)	6.7 (6.6)	13.5 (13.7)	8.5 (8.6)		
3.	[Co(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -pht)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Pink	0.70,	295	480.1 (485.9)	43.9 (43.9)	6.3 (6.4)	11.6 (11.5)	7.6 (7.3)	4.7	1.68
	[CoC ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					41.1 (41.1)	6.7 (6.6)	13.5 (13.7)	8.5 (8.6)		
4.	[Ni(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -ala)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Brown	0.53,	300	411.2 (409.5)	41.1 (41.0)	6.7 (6.6)	13.5 (13.7)	8.5 (8.6)	2.7	2.24
	[NiC ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					43.8 (43.8)	7.2 (7.1)	12.7 (12.8)	8.0 (8.1)		
5.	[Ni(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -val)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Brown	0.59,	310	431.5 (437.6)	43.8 (43.9)	7.2 (7.1)	12.7 (12.8)	8.0 (8.1)	3.0	2.01
	[NiC ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					49.2 (49.4)	6.5 (6.4)	11.6 (11.5)	7.4 (7.3)		
6.	[Ni(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -pht)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Brown	0.68,	350	478.4 (485.6)	49.2 (49.4)	6.5 (6.4)	11.6 (11.5)	7.4 (7.3)	2.9	1.22
	[NiC ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					40.4 (40.5)	6.4 (6.5)	13.4 (13.5)	8.4 (8.5)		
7.	[Cu(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -ala)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Green	0.54,	310	410.2 (414.4)	40.4 (40.5)	6.4 (6.5)	13.4 (13.5)	8.4 (8.5)	1.9	0.88
	[CuC ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					43.3 (43.4)	7.1 (7.0)	12.5 (12.6)	8.0 (8.0)		
8.	[Cu(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -val)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Green	0.57,	300	444.3 (442.4)	43.3 (43.4)	7.1 (7.0)	12.5 (12.6)	8.0 (8.0)	2.0	1.27
	[CuC ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]					48.7 (48.9)	6.4 (6.3)	11.5 (11.4)	7.3 (7.2)		
9.	[Cu(CDOSC)(<i>L</i> -pht)(H ₂ O)Cl]	Green	0.65,	330	480.1 (490.5)	48.7 (48.9)	6.4 (6.3)	11.5 (11.4)	7.3 (7.2)	2.1	1.30
	[CuC ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl]										

d = decomposition temperature.

Table 2. Infrared spectral vibrations and electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) for mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with CDOSC and amino acid (AA)

Complex	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)(\text{AA})$	$\nu(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$	Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1})
$(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{N})$ L-Alanine	-	-	-	-	-	3250 (as)	1588 (as)	-	-	-	-	-
$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})$ L-Valine	-	-	-	-	-	2940 (s) 3275 (as) 2960 (s)	1418 (s) 1650 (as) 1430 (s)	-	-	-	-	-
$(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})$ 1-Phenylalanine (CDOSC)	3475 (as) 3284 (s)	3160 3080	1690 1663	1625 1610	948 943	- 3130 (as) 2945 (s)	- 1570 (as) 1450 (s)	- 790	- 390	- 590	- 305	- 8820, 14475, 21052
$[\text{Co}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-alal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3485 (as) 3275 (s)	3166 3112	1663 1630	1615 1613	945 943	3160 (as) 2929 (s)	1590 (as) 1480 (s)	896	410	560	435	8692, 14540, 18654
$[\text{Co}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-val})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3360 (as) 3285 (s)	3158 3125	1630 1650	1615 1613	945 943	3160 (as) 2990 (s)	1590 (as) 1478 (s)	896	422	560	315	8693, 14325, 20346
$[\text{Co}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-phe})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3355 (as) 3285 (s)	3164 3107	1650 1667	1613 1620	943 932	3190 (as) 2990 (s)	1600 (as) 1478 (s)	926	395	585	360	9994, 16540, 24787
$[\text{Ni}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-alal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3436 (as) 3256 (s)	3125 3071	1667 1665	1620 1595	932 949	3120 (as) 2952 (s)	1580 (as) 1478 (s)	765	425	590	450	10246, 16342, 24867
$[\text{Ni}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-val})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3457 (as) 3244 (s)	3177 3100	1665 1660	1595 1595	949 936	3232 (as) 2950 (s)	1630 (as) 1435 (s)	972	425	590	420	10210, 16257, 24886
$[\text{Ni}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-phe})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3224 (as) 3240 (s)	3324 3048	1660 1652	1595 1616	936 939	3195 (as) 2945 (s)	1540 (as) 1463 (s)	816	415	600	325	13500, 18540
$[\text{Cu}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-alal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3457 (as) 3294 (s)	3148 3106	1652 1654	1616 1598	939 943	3165 (as) 2943 (s)	1550 (as) 1454 (s)	825	405	510	315	13648, 18245
$[\text{Cu}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-val})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3489 (as) 3254 (s)	3144 3082	1654 1667	1598 1606	943 936	3175 (as) 2956 (s)	1540 (as) 1472 (s)	-	460	525	350	14120, 17978
$[\text{Cu}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-phe})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3459 (as) 3324 (s)	3158 3073	1667 1667	1606 1606	936 936	3257 (as) 2956 (s)	1540 (as) 1485 (s)	820	430	540	350	14120, 17978

as = asymmetric stretching.
s = symmetric stretching.

The comparison of the spectra of CDOSC with those of its metal complexes viz. $[\text{Co}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-ala})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ allow us to determine the coordinating atoms in all the complexes. In the complexes, CDOSC acts as a bidentate ligand, coordinating through the carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-$). This mode of complexation is also supported by the shifting of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ towards lower wave numbers i.e. 1663 and 1610 cm^{-1} .

In case of chelation through amino acids, the IR spectra show significant features in the νNH_2 and νCOO^- region. The free amino acids exist as zwitterions ($-\text{H}_3\text{N}^+-\text{C}(\text{R})-\text{H}-\text{COO}^-$). This dipolar ion structure also accounts for the absence of acidic and basic properties of amino acids. The IR spectra of these are entirely different from those of metal complexes as in metal complexes, amino acids do not exist as zwitterions. The NH_3^+ end gets deprotonated on addition of NaOH to the amino acid to form sodium salt. Hence, in metal complexes amino acids coordinate through neutral NH_2 group and show an upward shift from range 3120–3010 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}-\text{H}_3$ function) to 3495–3300 cm^{-1} ⁷. In the present complexes, IR spectra show characteristic bands in the region 3200–3025 cm^{-1} which are lower in comparison of those of free νNH_2 . Thus, it is shown that nitrogen of free amino group participates in coordination. The IR spectral data of carboxylate group support its involvement in the coordination. The νCOO^- (sym) shows negative shifts while νCOO^- (asym) shows positive shifts which confirms the monodenticity of carboxylate group⁵. Thus, it has been concluded that amino acids act as monobasic bidentate ligand in these complexes and coordinate through amino nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen⁸. The presence of the coordinated water molecules is confirmed by non ligand bands in the range 972–765 cm^{-1} due to the rocking and wagging mode of water molecules. The $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ stretchings show low intensity bands in the range 600–305 cm^{-1} .

The electronic spectral data of all the complexes are given in Table 2. Complexes 1, 2 and 3 show multiple bands assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions of the d^7 system. Thus the octahedral geometry is proposed for cobalt complexes⁹. The electronic spectra of complexes 4, 5 and 6 show multiple bands which are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions of d^8 system thus the octahedral geometry (Fig. 1) is assigned to nickel complexes⁹. The electronic spectra of complexes 7, 8 and 9 show two characteristic bands in range 13500–18700 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$. The ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition is usually not observed as a separate band in tetragonal field. These transitions characterize d^9 system. Hence distorted octahedral geometry is assigned to copper complexes⁹.

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{AA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$, where $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$ for L-alanine, L-valine and L-phenylalanine.

The magnetic momenta (Table 1) lie between 4.0–4.9 B. M. for 1, 2 and 3 complexes of Co^{II} are indicative of three unpaired electrons¹⁰ each in these systems having high spin octahedral geometry. The magnetic momenta of Ni^{II} complexes 4, 5 and 6 lie between 2.7–3.0 B.M. showing d^8 system with two unpaired electrons. The magnetic momenta of Cu^{II} complexes 7, 8 and 9 lie between 1.98 to 2.02 B.M. indicate one unpaired electron each in these systems.

Table 3. Antifungal activity of ligands and their corresponding metal complexes

Comps.	Average percentage of inhibition after 72 h			
	<i>F. moniliformae</i>		<i>M. phaseolina</i>	
	100 ppm	400 ppm	100 ppm	400 ppm
(CDOSC)	37.31	48.69	40.97	70.04
$[\text{Co}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-ala})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	39.75	60.79	41.75	68.52
$[\text{Ni}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-ala})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	39.55	52.09	42.80	70.44
$[\text{Cu}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-ala})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	40.29	54.11	41.95	68.52
$[\text{Co}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-phe})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	37.92	52.44	49.04	72.61
$[\text{Ni}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-phe})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	40.22	56.86	48.54	67.85
$[\text{Cu}(\text{CDOSC})(\text{L-phe})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	40.46	52.27	52.01	71.92

Antifungal screening :

The ligand CDOSC as well as its complexes have been screened for antifungal activity against *Fusarium moniliformae* and *Macrophomina phaseolina*. The results are given in Table 3. The susceptibility of fungi towards complex compounds was tested by the food poison technique. Culture media for growing fungi consist of dried and scrubbed potato, dextrose, agar-agar and distilled water.

Medium with only DMSO was inoculated with pathogen served as control. Three replicates were used in each case. The linear growth after 3 days was obtained and present inhibition was calculated according to Vincent's formula¹¹.

The observed results revealed an enhancement of the antifungal activity of ligand in the form of its metal complexes which can be well explained in the light of chelation theory¹².

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade and their solutions were prepared by dissolving requisite amounts of

samples in double distilled ethanol. The citral (E. Merck, India) was used as such. CDOSC was synthesized as per literature procedure¹³.

IR spectra were recorded on a FTIR spectrophotometer model IR-550 NICOLET-USA in the 4000–200 cm⁻¹ region employing KBr pellets. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian CARY 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were obtained at CDRI, Lucknow. Molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic method using Beckmann's thermometer and magnetic moments were measured by Gouy method. Chlorine content was estimated by Volhard's method and metals were estimated by reported methods¹³. The purity of compound was checked by TLC using ethylacetate and hexane in 1 : 2 ratio.

Synthesis of ligand :

cis-3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadienemicarbazone (CDOSC) : To an aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and crystalline sodium acetate (0.01 mol) was added an ethanolic solution of citral (0.01 mol) dropwise with continuous stirring. To remove the turbidity of the mixture, ethanol (double distilled) was added until clear solution was obtained. After 1 h refluxing on water bath on cooling CDOSC precipitated. It was filtered and finally washed from hot distill water. The semicarbazone gave satisfactory analysis and spectral properties.

Synthesis of complexes :

The complexes have been synthesized by mixing equimolar amount of ethanolic solutions of CDOSC (0.002 mol) and sodium salt of L-ala or L-val or L-phe (0.002 mol) to ethanolic solution containing 0.002 mol of metal dichloride (in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio) with continuous stirring for 3 h. The above mixture was kept on refluxing for 3 h, 28 h and 20 h for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. The precipitated complex was filtered and washed with distill water and ethanol (to remove unreacted materials and impurities).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for recording elemental analyses. One of the authors, Shikha Rawat is thankful to Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi, India for awarding

Senior Research Fellowship. Thanks are also to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. P. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 2778; R. Sharma, A. K. Bansal and M. Nagar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 2255; S. Rawat, R. Sharma and M. Nagar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 26; A. K. Bansal, P. L. Sharma and M. Nagar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 26.
2. K. H. Reddy, M. S. Babu, P. S. Babu and S. Dayananda, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1233; A. A. E. Asmy, M. E. Khalifa and M. M. Hassanian, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 92.
3. N. Kanoongo, R. Shingh and J. P. Tandon, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 135; A. Garg and J. P. Tanden, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 212; K. K. Aravindaksan and K. Muralcedharan, *React. Solids*, 1990, **8**, 91.
4. D. X. West, J. J. Ingram, N. M. Kozub, G. A. Bain and A. E. Liberta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 213; D. X. West, N. M. Kozub and G. A. Bain, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 52; D. X. West, M. A. Lockwood, A. E. Liberta, X. Chem and R. D. Willet, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1993, **18**, 221.
5. A. C. Green, H. Place, R. D. Willett and J. I. Legg, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 4672; S. Kasselouri, A. Garoufis and N. Hadjiliadis, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1987, **23**, 135; K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970; L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 3rd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1975.
6. A. N. Singh, R. P. Singh, J. G. Mohanty and A. Chakrovorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 2597.
7. A. Iakovidis, N. Hadjiliadis, H. Schollhorn, V. Thewatt and G. Trotscher, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1989, **164**, 221; S. Kasselovri and N. Hadpiliadis, 1990, **168**, 15; S. H. Lauri, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 2597.
8. A. C. Green, H. Place, R. D. Willett and J. I. Legg, 1986, **25**, 4672; R. Ilavarasi, M. S. N. Rao and M. R. Udupa, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1997, **109**, 79.
9. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
10. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, "Progress in Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1964; J. Lewis and R. G. Wilkins, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967.
11. I. M. Vincent, *Nature*, 1927, 159.
12. W. H. R. Shaw, *Nature*, 1961, **192**, 754.
13. A. I. Vogel, "Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., ELBS, London, 1989; A. I. Vogel, "Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., ELBS, London, 1989.